

1 **Tfh from humans with MS are ALDH9A1+ and ALDH18A1+.**

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6 We are interested in identification of cell of origin in human disease involving autoimmunity and
7 inflammation. Immune cell profiling has the potential to identify cell populations with aggressive,
8 immunogenic capacity based on expression of specific cell state markers which is difficult to conduct using
9 whole blood. We positively demonstrate here that T follicular helper (Tfh) cells isolated from humans with
10 Multiple Sclerosis are positive for ALDH9A1+ and ALDH18A1+.

11 Citations

12 1. Börnsen, L., Ratzner, R., Piehl, F., Khademi, M., Olsson, T., Sørensen, P.S. and Sellebjerg, F.,
13 2013. Systemic inflammation in progressive multiple sclerosis involves follicular T-helper, Th17-and
14 activated B-cells and correlates with progression. PloS one, 8(3), pp.e57820-e57820.
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